

HEURISTIC TEACHING: POSSIBILITIES AND ADVANTAGES

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Abstract. *The purpose of the study is to reveal the importance of the selected methods in organizing the educational process in today's education system, which will make students flexible, creative thinkers, and develop their intellectual potential. Heuristic education, its capabilities and advantages, were chosen as an example. Information about this type of education is provided, and the characteristics of heuristic education methods are studied in detail. Based on the analysis of theoretical materials, the history of the origin of the concept of "heuristic education", its initial popularization by mathematicians, the essence of "heuristic education methods", the concepts of the science of heuristics, and the areas of application of heuristics are shown. In addition, the article provides information about the specific characteristics, advantages and disadvantages of heuristic education methods, and methods of application. From the study, we can understand that among the heuristic teaching methods: "Multidimensional - Matrix Method (Morphological Analysis Method)" and "Free Association Method" are mainly adapted to an adult audience due to their critical and in-depth analytical approach. We recommend the "heuristic question method" as a relatively uncomplicated method that helps to improve fluent speech and is suitable for audiences of all ages. In conclusion, Heuristic teaching is an effective teaching method in the learning process that allows students to think independently, approach the problem creatively, implement practice, and discover theories on their own.*

Keywords: *heuristics, heuristic method, heuristic science, history of emergence, heuristic activity, heuristic educational methods.*

Introduction. Today, in a modern educational environment, pedagogical technologies and innovative approaches play an important role in improving the quality of education. This is especially reflected in the field of social and humanitarian sciences, with the help of which teachers, along with organizing the educational process more effectively, constantly develop their own creative potential. Social and humanitarian and pedagogical sciences are aimed at studying such important issues as the development of society and the maturation of a person as a well-rounded individual, culture and historical heritage, and the pedagogical creativity and innovative approaches of teachers in these areas create the basis for increasing productivity in the educational process. These reasons require changing traditional forms of education to new interactive forms. Accordingly, the use of innovative approaches, interactive methods, including heuristic teaching methods, and the systematic integration of innovations into the educational process by teachers in their professional activities contribute to increasing the quality of education. In such educational processes, which model real situations, encourage logical thinking in educational terms, and serve to develop thinking, the student actively participates and becomes the main subject of the relationship. In addition, the participation of everyone is ensured in the training sessions, rather than being a passive audience.

One of the unique manifestations of the new innovative approach is heuristic education. The word heuristics comes from the Greek language and is derived from the word "heurist", which means "I seek", "I find", or "I discovered" [1]. Heuristics is a science that studies the creative aspects of human thinking, as well as a set of methods and approaches used in solving problems. Heuristic approaches are especially useful in making quick and effective decisions in complex or uncertain situations. We can see Socrates as a prototype of heuristic education. Maieutics was created by Socrates as a method of obtaining hidden knowledge in each person through leading questions [2]. During the conversation, Socrates constantly asks questions to confirm one or another truth, and answering them, the interlocutor formulates statements that are unknown to him. Although a brief, somewhat cryptic mention of analysis and synthesis in heuristic learning is given in Book 13 of some, but not all, editions of Euclid's Elements, a more precise explanation of these two methods is given in the 4th century by the Greek Pappus, who explains that two slightly different analyses can be used to try and find proofs [3]. The French philosopher and mathematician R. Dexter, who were engaged in it, concluded that "heuristic methods are universal methods [4]. The heuristic education method has a long history, more precisely, it dates back to antiquity. The main feature of this method is the orientation of students in the educational process with questions aimed at more independent problem solving and the development of thinking activity in the process of answering. Heuristic conversations are usually organized through directed, sequential questions, and the student's interest in problems increases, he actively participates in solving them. This method is used in pedagogy as a purposeful and productive form of activity aimed at developing student thinking.

Heuristic teaching methods were initially widely used in the field of mathematics. They are known as the "art of mathematical solving" methods developed by mathematicians. After Al-Khwarizmi, who lived in the 9th century, introduced the concept of algorithm into science, it was concluded that the inversion method of heuristics could help in solving algorithmic problems, although the heuristic direction was opposite to the algorithmic one [5]. Later, this method began to be used in other subjects as an advanced and universal method. At the same time, heuristics serve as an important tool in the educational process to develop students' independent thinking and improve their ability to solve problems. Jan Amos Komensky emphasized the need to introduce the concept of heuristic teaching into the education system as one of the advanced pedagogical methods [6]. He defines the heuristic method in the educational process as "a person who creates various innovations is brought up in the context of a person's thinking and creative thinking [7]. In addition, heuristic education in pedagogy was studied by P.F. Kapterev, I. Andreev, A.V. Khutorskaya, and the oldest example of the use of heuristic methods in Russian pedagogy was the "living word" methodology, which was formed in the second half of the 19th century in the journal "Philological Notes" by A.A. Khovansky. The heuristic education method began to spread to us from the second half of the 20th century. In particular, the introduction of cybernetics into the educational process, in connection with the increase in scientific research, creativity, and innovation, led to its widespread use in the educational process. Currently, the direction of heuristics in science is also developing. According to this direction, after the idea of creating something new is put forward, a new voluntary action program is drawn up. To overcome or accelerate this situation, innovation is created through new creative, non-standard thinking. The thinking process is carried out through analysis, synthesis, and generalization, and certain operations are sequentially solved and resolved through a new approach. From a cognitive-psychological point of view: Heuristics are "mental shortcuts" used to make quick and effective

decisions in complex situations, which serve to find a “good enough” decision or a quick solution [8]. They are not completely ideal solutions, but they save effort and time. According to the analysis introduced by Tversky and Kahneman, heuristics encourage people to make decisions in conditions of complexity and lack of information [9].

The science of heuristics teaches as a methodological basis and theoretical approach to problem solving, creation and creative search.

The main tasks of heuristics as a science are as follows:

1. Study of productive processes: it is to analyze the processes of human perception and memory in solving complex problems, rapid, sufficient “mental shortcuts” in real situations.

2. Creating conditions for heuristic activity: In scientific theory, scientists consider heuristic approaches, that is, an “adaptive toolbox” - a set of flexible strategies used to make quick and effective life decisions [10]. The development of these conditions through a model is widely used in scientific research.

3. Modeling heuristic activity: in the scientific process, it organizes effective heuristic activity by identifying the stages of problem analysis, model construction, evaluation and improvement

4. Formation of the laws of a goal-oriented heuristic system: it helps to systematically apply methods such as analogy, induction, simplification in solving problems by establishing them on a scientific basis.

5. Creation of technical constructs for the application of heuristic activity: aims to develop opportunities for the implementation of heuristic strategies in real situations through practical and technical means, algorithmic approaches. Although this point is not directly mentioned in traditional cognitive psychology models, it is widely used today in the fields of computer science and artificial intelligence to create technical solutions based on heuristic algorithms. These constructs serve to further increase the possibility of applying practical, effective heuristic activities. Heuristic activities are important in the formation of creative and metacognitive skills, in stimulating creativity in design and engineering, and serve the development of behavior, creativity and metacognitive skills in a person [11]. During the activity, heuristic strategies (for example, “working forward” or “working backward”) simplify the solution of mathematical or scientific problems, as well as develop metacognitive (thinking process) skills.

In the process of learning in scientific and pedagogical fields, heuristic activities have a positive effect on the student’s academic performance, independent thinking, teamwork and self-organization skills. In special creative approaches, heuristics are used as an important strategy for generating new and original ideas. For example, “idea-trigger” heuristics provide solutions superior to brainstorming. Heuristic methods are specific strategies used in educational methods: becoming, inductive approach, constructive approach, etc.

Areas of application of heuristics:

• **Within the field of psychology:** Heuristics is a term used to describe a person's quick and intuitive approaches to decision-making, for example, the concept of "heuristics" refers to a person's assessment of the probability of an event based on how easy it is to remember. This can sometimes lead to making wrong decisions.

• **In computer science:** Heuristic algorithms are methods that, although they do not guarantee a clear and optimal solution, are used in practice as methods that help to quickly and adequately solve a problem and solve complex problems.

• **In pedagogical education:** Heuristic approaches are considered as a means of education used to develop students' independent thinking, to train competitive specialists who can express their attitude to the knowledge being studied, and to put forward new thoughts, ideas and proposals.

• **From a philosophical point of view:** Heuristics is the art of discovering innovations and a methodology for scientific research. It studies the creative aspects of human thinking.

We can cite the following as effective methods of heuristic education:

1. The heuristic question method in modern pedagogical approaches puts the student at the center of the problem: the teacher does not give a ready-made answer, but, with guidance, encourages the student to analyze the problem. This approach creates an opportunity to discover the main idea - that is, the "optimal idea" in understanding and solving the problem. This methodology prefers to teach complex knowledge through small tasks, step-by-step analysis. This stimulates a controlled process of mastery in the learner and helps to solve the problem step by step, not all at once. Lessons structured on the basis of the method encourage students to take a creative approach to solving the problem and think intuitively.

Advantages of this approach:

-Deeper understanding of the problem through exploration and discovery based on free activity.

-Encourages analysis and thinking of alternative assumptions and options.

Weaknesses:

- Does not guarantee absolute success: using heuristic questions does not increase the guarantee of a perfect or true solution to the problem - on the contrary, it can sometimes lead to incorrect or superficial solutions.

- Distraction and time: students are initially confused by unclear questions, which makes it difficult to make a clear decision, and this method can also take more time than traditional methods.

2. Multidimensional - Matrix Method (Morphological Analysis Method) - a method created by the Swiss astronomer Zwicky [12], is a method for systematically analyzing multidimensional, uncertain, and non-quantifiable problems.

This method is expressed in the form of a "morphological table" or "Zwicky box": the options for the parameters that make up the problem are placed in the columns and rows of the table. Using this method, illogical combinations are filtered out and realistic solutions are isolated. This method, originally discovered by Zwicky in the early 1940s [13], is used in scientific circles to describe methods for understanding the structural and functional relationships between the components of a larger object. The word comes from the Greek morphos, meaning "form," which is combined with the suffix -ology ("study") to achieve its meaning: the study of form. Morphology is considered to have disciplinary applications.

Advantages of the method:

- Creativity and the birth of new ideas: The method is often used as a powerful tool for generating innovative solutions and ideas. For example, teachers use morphological analysis in conjunction with Brainstorming to increase the creative potential of students, as a result of which students have the opportunity to significantly improve their creative skills.

- Can be used as an experiment in practical studies.

The main disadvantages of the method:

- A large number of options: For problems of medium difficulty, the number of parameters and options can be very large. In this case, choosing the most optimal combination in the table becomes very difficult.

- Cannot reveal every parameter: The method may not provide a complete picture of all the parameters in the problem; that is, some uncertain or contextual factors may not be included in the system.

- Requires high skills: Dividing the problem into parameters and variants, creating tables, filtering and analyzing them - these require a high level of methodological and creative skills.

Some elements of the problem are known, and some are unknown - this is an analogue when choosing this method, because morphological analysis is useful in such cases, that is, it allows you to search for new ideas by dividing the problem into parameters and analyzing the variants of each. The method ensures a systematic approach, considering the combinatorial nature of the parameters, which helps to reduce the uncertainty in the problem and prevent errors. This method requires working with complexity and variants, and accordingly, the audience is required to be ready for methodology and analytical thinking.

3. Free association is a creative approach that is presented without critical filters, stimulating the flow of free thoughts, imagination, and ideas that are not separated from the minds of students or the team. In this method, new associative connections are formed in the process of finding a solution, which in turn stimulates innovative thinking. This process, based on expanding semantic distance, enhances creativity. This method is a powerful tool in creative approaches and creative activities, supporting new ideas and connections. It stimulates intensive thinking, group creativity, and helps to bring the problem to an intuitive solution. Such associative processes are generally associated with creative thinking and are linked to divergent thinking, which is an important component of creativity. In fact, associative abilities are used to explain half of the individual differences in divergent thinking indicators [14]. These abilities in a person are revealed through constant self-improvement and similar methods. However, order, moderation, and audience selection are important for the effective use of this method.

Research shows that free association is the basis of creative thinking. It works to form complex ideas and create innovative connections between ambiguous concepts. The free association method increases the creative atmosphere in the group. As a result of synergy, each participant adds their own unique vision and ideas, which allows for a new set of ideas to be generated, allowing the problem to be viewed in a broader context. Through this process, connections between the external environment and internal thoughts are created.

Benefits:

- **Creative discovery:** innovative ideas emerge through new and unexpected connections;
- **Accelerated solution:** the free flow of ideas helps solve the problem in a broader and freer context.

- **Cognitive flexibility:** students or group members are flexible in generating ideas independently, using non-logical connections

- **Encourage collaboration:** students exchange ideas in the process of synthesizing several ideas through group meetings and discussions, which leads to a holistic and comprehensive solution.

Disadvantages and some relative limitations:

- **Risk of loss of structure:** with increased freedom, ideas can become disorganized and confusing;

• **Need for moderation:** it can be difficult to maintain a positive environment, organize thoughts, and work effectively without numerical or other structural aids to achieve the expected result;

• **Audience suitability:** Young children may have difficulty controlling their chaotic flow of thoughts — this method is mainly suitable for a higher-educated, logically-minded audience, as well as for andragogical education.

4. Inversion method - this means solving the problem through a "reverse" approach: we are required to consider the opposite of the solution we usually seek to the problem. Accordingly, the name of the method - invert - means "to overturn", "to overturn". "Invert, always invert" - the famous principle for solving difficult problems put forward by the German mathematician Carl Jacobi also indicates this [15]. That is, this method makes it possible to identify errors, mental blocks related to the problem and find a new approach. For example, when solving a maze, instead of usually starting from the starting point, working from the end point is an example of inversion. This requires the student to be more logical and analyze the given task in all aspects, and this method expands the range of thinking. Another noteworthy aspect is that the inversion method is an effective tool for breaking away from stereotypes and identifying risks in advance. This approach pays special attention to the idea of "achieving perfection", not "avoiding mistakes". Inversion methods in education help to discover new solutions and approaches by thinking about the problem in reverse, and to form creative ideas.

Advantages: Identification of errors and blocks, innovations and creative solutions, sustainable strategies,

Disadvantages: Time-consuming, can lead to excessive negativity, delays the transition from analysis to practice.

Conclusion

So, as a result of the above research, we can say that Heuristic learning is an effective method of education that allows students to think independently, implement practice, and discover theories on their own. Scientific research has supported the fact that this method enhances creative thinking, creative approaches, metacognitive skills, and interest in learning in many subjects. However, this approach may not always be more effective than traditional direct teaching, especially when students do not have sufficient basic knowledge or resources in the subject being studied. Some disadvantages of heuristic learning methods are observed. These disadvantages are relatively minor and do not negatively affect the essence of heuristic learning. The methods and techniques selected based on the professional knowledge and accumulated experience of the teacher make the learning process more meaningful and beneficial, and help students develop creative approaches and new ideas.

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